

PROBABILISTIC CHARACTERIZATION OF POROSITY DEFECT IN A LAMINATED COMPOSITE

Edouard Gauthier¹, Laurent Guillaumat²

¹ IRT Jules Verne, Chemin du Chaffault 44340 Bouguenais France
<http://www.irt-jules-verne.fr>

E-mail : edouard.gauthier@irt-jules-verne.fr

² LAMPA ENSAM, 2 Boulevard du Ronceray 49100 Angers France
<http://lampa.ensam.eu>

E-mail : laurent.guillaumat@ensam.eu

Keywords: Defect, Porosity, Probabilistic characterization, Variability, Image analysis

ABSTRACT

During the manufacturing process of laminated composites, whatever the process used, defects may appear within the material. Porosity defect is defined by the presence of small cavities which contains gaseous matter, which are called pores and which are categorized according to their size (micro, meso and macro-pores).

Different porosity characterization approaches exist, and because pores are geometric defects, we used image analysis by optical microscopy. This method allows us to visualize the pores directly inside the material. Two types of porosity are studied in this paper.

This work presents the deterministic and probabilistic characterization of the porosity for a glass/epoxy laminated composite by comparing plates manufactured with different processing parameters.

The variability of different parameters is studied by analysing the results, identifying distributions of the value of these parameters and the distribution law that best models them. The porosity between the two materials and their variability are finally compared.

1 INTRODUCTION

The design of structures in composite material takes into account the mechanical behaviour of the composite, in static, fatigue and dynamic loading. For it, the study of the composite is made to understand the mechanical behaviour by determine parameters like Young's modulus, shear's modulus, Poisson coefficient or failure stresses.

These parameters have some variability [1] due to two reasons. The first one is the microstructural variability like change in the fiber orientation or the fiber rate [2], and can be a strong influence. The second one is the presence of defects like delamination, wrinkle or porosity, and has a significant influence on static and fatigue behaviour [3-6]. These defects may appear during the manufacturing process due to the non-homogeneous nature of composite materials, whatever the process used.

Porosity is a geometric defect created during the process and defined by cavities which contain gaseous matter and which is called pores. It is due to a poor extraction of air because of different parameters like the matrix viscosity, the vacuum pressure or the humidity during the storage of the material.

The presence of pores inside a composite significantly degrades the mechanical properties in static and in fatigue, where pores can act as a failure initiation points [6-7]. That is why identification and characterization are important for determining the quality of a composite structure.

Different techniques exist to characterize porosity in a composite like Archimedes theoretical versus Actual Density, Matrix burn-off, Matrix digestion, image analysis by optical microscopy or SEM, and X-ray computed tomography or micro-computed tomography. In this paper, the porosity is defined by image analysis using optical microscopy. It is a destructive analysis technique which allows the porosity rate, the pores size, shape and distribution to be analysed [7]. It is important to characterize all these parameters to define the porosity that is effective to the material.

A sample, which has a porosity rate of 2% with only one pore, will have a very different mechanical behaviour than a sample which has the same porosity rate but with several pores. The second one leads to smaller porosity size.

This paper presents the deterministic characterization of two different states of porosity and the comparison of the different parameters of them. In order to be able to characterize in a probabilistic way, a large number of samples are analysed which allow to observe a large quantity of pores and thus the different variations of the characteristic parameters of the porosity.

2 EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

2.1 Materials

This study use a prepreg laminate composite of glass/epoxy manufactured by Krempel©. The laminate is implemented in an oven under temperature and pressure. To observe two types of porosity, plates are manufactured with different values of characteristics parameters to vary resin viscosity. The first type of plate, IN1242, is applied at a temperature T_1 , a pressure P_1 for a time t_1 . In order to have a second type of plates with a porosity rate higher, the other type of plate, IN1250, is implemented with a time $t_2 < t_1$, to not allow pores to withdraw into themselves, and so to respect the cure cycle of the prepreg, under a temperature $T_2 > T_1$. The implement of plates is made by AIC Composite, an affiliate company of Europe Technologie and the plate dimensions are 350 mm x 150mm x 2mm.

2.2 Sample treatment

Samples are cut from plates with a circular saw with dimensions of 20mm x 5mm x 2mm and cutting of samples is made in transversal for UD 0°. Samples are cold-coated with an epoxy or acrylic resin in a cylindrical mold. Flat cross-sections of sample are prepared by a polishing with a struers buffer at different grain of polishing : a first mechanical polishing with grinding foils from 320 to 4000 and, with a polishing cloth MD-Dur and a suspension AP-A of 1µm; and a second mechanical and chemical polishing with a polishing cloth MD-Chem and a suspension of OP-U Non dry of 0.04µm.

2.3 Image analysis by optical microscopy

Image of cross-section of each sample is made by optical microscopy with a Zeiss Axio Imager and an image acquisition software AxioVisio. Each photo is taken with a magnification of x100 because image can't be too heavy. A pre-study was made to define the influence of resolution on the porosity rate measurement and concluded that resolution after a certain stage has no influence with an increase of only 0.04% of the porosity rate between a resolution of 0.5pixels/µm and 2pixels/µm. Acquisition of grayscale images was made to make the thresholding easier, colour's images in 24-bit is converted in a gray's images in 8-bit. Each pixel of images varies between 0 for black to 255 for white.

Each image is treated with an open-software Gimp to fill each pore which is not clearly black or which is white because coat resin fills it. Figure 6 shows this step.

The numerical analysis of microscopy images is carried out using a image analysis open-software ImageJ. The software analyses the individual pixel and select each pixel between 0 and a selected value between 80 and 120, which is called an event pixel N_p . The figure 3 shows the thresholding step with the selection of upper value. The selected value is chosen to not take account fibre, matrix, unwanted noise or outliers. To measure the surface porosity rate A_p , ImageJ calculate ratio of event pixels on total pixels of the picture N_i .

$$A_p = N_p / N_i \quad (1)$$

Figure 1-4 show the different steps for analysis of microscopy images with ImageJ.

Figure 1 : Image opening.

Figure 2 : Scale definition.

Figure 3: Thresholding.

Figure 4 : Porosity rate measurement.

Once the porosity rate is measured, other parameters of pores are measured: the two diameters that characterize a pore d and D , as well as the distance L between two pores as presented in the figure 5.

Figure 5 : Measurement of the two diameters d and D , and distance L

3 RESULTS

For each plate, 8 samples are analyzed and each sample is characterized by a first cross-section, which is called sample x , and a second cross-section 3mm under the first one which is called sample $x+3\text{mm}$.

3.1 Type 1: IN1250

Figure 6 shows a sample of the type 1 plate before and after the image processing with Gimp. Several pores have to be filled with black pixels like those surrounded by the red circle.

Figure 6 : Microscopy image of a sample 2+3mm of IN1250 before and after the image processing.

Sample 2+3mm shows pores with certain variability in the shape, which is more like ellipsoidal and with dispersion more and less global. There is no pores concentration in samples IN1250. This condition remains in the other samples like in the figure 7 which present the cross-section of sample 7.

Figure 7 : Microscopy image of sample 7 of plate IN1250.

Results of porosity rate for each sample are announced in the table 1. Mean μ_p , standard deviation σ_p and coefficient of variation CV are calculated and presented in the table 1. Results have a significant variability with a CV of 43.5%

3.2 Type 2: IN1242

Figure 8 presents two samples of plate IN1242, sample 1 above and sample 7 below.

Figure 8 : Microscopy images of sample 1 above and sample 7 below from plate IN1242.

Samples of plate IN1242 present less pores than samples of IN1250. Like for samples IN1250, they have some rich fiber/resin area but because pores are fewer, samples have some pores concentration. Pores concentrations are not plentiful and they are dispersed randomly. Pores seem to be smaller than pores of plate IN1250. Also like samples IN1250, porosity rate has a significant variability with a CV of 37.8%. Figure 9 shows the variability of porosity rate for IN1250 and IN1242.

Sample IN1250	Porosity Average [%]	Sample IN1242	Porosity Average [%]
1	1.642	1	1.508
2	2.269	2	0.566
3	2.307	3	0.467
4	4.345	4	1.292
5	2.473	5	1.093
6	1.852	6	1.022
7	2.404	7	1.069
8	1.057	8	1.382
1 + 3mm	1.342	1 + 3mm	1.649
2 + 3mm	4.748	2 + 3mm	0.672
3 + 3mm	4.085	3 + 3mm	0.811
4 + 3mm	4.331	4 + 3mm	2.238
5 + 3mm	3.213	5 + 3mm	1.638
6 + 3mm	3.024	6 + 3mm	1.324
7 + 3mm	3.993	7 + 3mm	1.113
8 + 3mm	5.426	8 + 3mm	1.307
μ_p	3.032	μ_p	1.197
σ_p	1.318	σ_p	0.452
CV	0.435	CV	0.378

Table 1: Results of porosity rate for plate IN1250 and IN1242.

Figure 9 : Histogram of porosity rate for IN1250 and IN1242.

4 PROBABILISTIC CHARACTERIZATION

First results of porosity rate for plate IN1242 and IN1250 show that porosity is a defect with a high variability, with porosity rate which can vary from 1% to 5% in 3mm of thickness as shows the sample 8 of IN1250. That's why a probabilistic characterization is necessary to have a better knowledge of the defect. For each sample, and for each pore, number of pores, diameter D and d , and the distance L between each pores, are measured, and the ratio R is calculated to define the shape of each pore. Results are treated to characterize the variability of parameters D , L and R .

4.1 Pores quantity

Figure 10 presents the number of pores per sample for plate IN1242 and IN1250. For a porosity rate of 1.2%, IN1242 has on average 41.2 pores per sample when for a porosity rate of 3%, IN1250 has on average 88.9 pores per sample. Also the range of value of number of pores per sample for IN1250 is more extensive than for IN1242.

Figure 10 : Histogram of numbers of pores for IN1250 and IN1242.

4.2 Pores diameter D

Figure 11 presents histograms of pores diameters D for IN1250 and IN1242 and table 2 shows the results of fitting parameters for a lognormal distribution. Histogram of IN1250 put more weight on larger pores than histogram of IN1242 with a higher mean value μ and a higher value of log standard deviation σ , which correspond with microscopy cross-section observations.

Figure 11 : Histogram of pores diameters D for IN1250 and IN1242.

$$f(x; \mu, \sigma) = \frac{1}{x\sigma\sqrt{2\pi}} \left(-\frac{(\ln x - \mu)^2}{2\sigma^2} \right) \quad (2)$$

Parameters	IN1250	Parameters	IN1242
μ	5.1405	μ	4.9045
σ	0.68122	σ	0.62526

Table 2 : Curve fitting parameters of D for plate IN1250 and IN1242.

Variability of parameter D is defined by a distribution law which is chosen by the best fitting. For that 3 distribution laws, Lognormal, Normal and Lorentz, are compared with 4 statistic tests : Adjuced R^2 , Reduced χ^2 , Residual sum of squares and Akaike's Information Criterion (AIC). The adjuced R^2 has to be maximized unlike the 3 other tests which have to be minimized. Table 3 and 4 shows results of statistic tests which all put Lognormal law as the best model for describe the variability of diameter D. This distribution law uses 2 parameters : the mean μ and the standard deviation σ of the variable's natural logarithm .Figure 9 shows the good fitting of lognormal law on the result of parameter D. Also, lognormal law take account the fact that D can't be negative, limiting his domain to $[0; +\infty]$.

So, pores diameter D in plate IN1242 and IN1250 can be modeled with the lognormal law which will describe realistically the dimensions of pores.

Test IN1242	Lognormal	Lorentz	Normal
Adj R^2	0.98182	0.90202	0.88867
Reduced χ^2	1.497E-4	8.071E-4	11.7E-4
Residual Sum of squares	1.65E-3	8.88E-3	12.84E-3
AIC	-120.09	-94.82	-89.28

Table 3 : Comparison of law distribution for IN1242.

Test IN1250	Lognormal	Lorentz	Normal
Adj R^2	0.99095	0.90869	0.88866
Reduced χ^2	2.676E-5	2.701E-4	3.293E-4
Residual Sum of squares	0.91E-3	9.18E-3	11.2E-3
AIC	-392.44	-304.59	-297.05

Table 4 : Comparison of law distribution for IN1250.

4.3 Pores diameters ratio R

The ratio R of diameters defines the global shape of pores: a circular shape has a ratio of 1 and an ellipsoidal shape has a ratio higher than 1. Figure 12 presents the ratio for samples of IN1242 and 1250 and table 5 shows results of distribution fitting for a lognormal distribution which is also the best fitting distribution for parameter R. Porosity in plate IN1250 put more weight on ellipsoidal shape with a mean value μ higher than IN1242 and with a log standard deviation value σ higher.

Figure 12 : Histogram of pores diameters ratio R for IN1250 and IN1242.

Parameters	IN1250	Parameters	IN1242
μ	0.48979	μ	0.4417
σ	0.41352	σ	0.34397

Table 5 : Curve fitting parameters of parameter R for plate IN1250 and IN1242.

4.3 Distance L between pores

Figure 13 presents the histogram of value of distance L between two pores, for plates IN1242 and IN1250, and Table 6 shows the value of lognormal distribution parameters which is again the best fitting distribution. The distance L between pores is higher for plate IN1242 than for IN1250 which agree with the fact that IN1242 has less pores and smaller pores dimensions than IN1250. Also, for IN1242, there are pores far from other ones with very high value of L which is not the case for IN1250 with only low value of L.

Figure 13 : Histogram of distance L between pores for IN1250 and IN1242.

Parameters	IN1250	Parameters	IN1242
μ	5.738	μ	6.3431
σ	0.66539	σ	0.83741

Table 6 : Curve fitting parameters of parameter L for plate IN1250 and IN1242.

4.3 Comparison between IN1250 and IN1242

IN1242 and IN1250 present two different porosity for the same material due to different manufacturing parameters. The first one has a porosity rate of 1.2% with pores well dispersed. The second one has a higher porosity rate of 3% with also well dispersed pores, but with pores which have a higher diameter D and which are more ellipsoidal. So IN1250 has bigger pores in shape and dimension, whether in mean value or in diameter D distribution which put more weight on higher D. Pores of IN1250 are bigger than pores of IN1242, but they also are more abundant. Finally, distance L between two pores is smaller for IN1250 than for IN1242 which agree with the fact that IN1250 has bigger pores and has more pores than IN1242. Small distance L between pores could create a path for the propagation of a crack. These differences between pores of IN1250 and IN1242 make that porosity average is different overall. Porosity rate is different for the 2 plates globally but also locally with higher variation of porosity rate for IN1250 than for IN1242.

Porosity for IN1250 should have a bigger effect on the mechanical behaviour than porosity for IN1242 not only because of the porosity rate, but also because of dimensions, shape and distribution of pores.

5 CONCLUSION

To study porosity defect in a laminate composite, 2 types of plates was made with different value of characteristic parameter, namely the cure temperature and the cure time. The first plate named IN1250 has a higher porosity rate than the second plate IN1242. The difference of porosity between IN1250 and IN1242 is not only on porosity rate, but also on pores number, shape, dimensions and distribution. After characterizing the porosity rate of different samples and the dimensions of each pores, results are treated to observe the variability of each parameters. Variability of diameter D of pores, of diameters ratio R and distance L between pores is identified with a distribution law to be able to model it.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This study is part of the SIMSCEF project managed by IRT Jules Verne (French Institute in Research and Technology in Advanced Manufacturing Technologies for Composite, Metallic and Hybrid Structures). The authors wish to associate the industrial and academic partners of this project; respectively ADWEN, DAHER, GEM Institute and LAMPA Institute.

REFERENCES

- [1] S. Sriramula, M. K. Chryssanthopoulos, An experimental characterisation of spatial variability in GFRP composite panels, *Structural Safety*, **42**, 2013, pp. 1-11 (<http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.strusafe.2013.01.002>)
- [2] Y. Davila, L. Crouzeix, B. Douchin, F. Collombet, Y-H. Grunevald, Study of the sources of variability of a CRFP composite structure cured in autoclave, *Comptes Rendus des JNC18*, 2013
- [3] D. O. Adams, M. W. Hyer, Effects of layer waviness on the compression strength of thermoplastic composite material, *Journal of Reinforced Plastics and Composites*, **12**, 1993, pp. 414 (<https://doi.org/10.1177/073168449301200404>)

- [4] L. D. Bloom, J. Wang, K. D. Potter, Damage progression and defect sensitivity : An experimental study of representative wrinkles in tension, *Composites Part B*, **45**, 2012, pp. 449-458 (<http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesb.2012.05.021>)

- [5] Y. Ledru, Etude de la porosité dans les matériaux composites stratifiés aéronautiques, *Thèse CROMeP*, 2009

- [6] S.F. Müller de Almeida, Z. Dos Santos Nogueira Neto, Effect of void content on the strength of composite laminates, *Composites Structures*, **28**, 1994, pp. 139-148 ([http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/0263-8223\(94\)90044-2](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/0263-8223(94)90044-2)).

- [7] L. Liu, B. Zhang, D. Wang, Z. Wu, Effects of cure cycles on void content and mechanical properties of composites laminates, *Composites Structures*, **73**, 2006, pp. 303-309 (<http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.compstruct.2005.02.001>).